

Synthesis of [2,4-Diarylyureido-6-yl-aminoceramidone]- s-triazine Derivatives

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The disperse dyes of the type [2,4-diarylyureido-6-yl-aminoceramidone]-s-triazine derivatives have been synthesised by condensation of bromamine acid with aniline, then desulphonation and cyclisation to obtained 8-aminoceramidone, followed by its cyanuration and condensation with various aryl urea. The dyeing properties of these dyes were studied on polyester fabrics.

BROMAMINE acid is the raw material to synthesise a number of anthraquinone disperse dyes¹⁻⁴. Hence, it was thought interesting to prepare some derivatives from bromamine acid, which could bring variation in the shades and fastness properties of dyes. Aryl-aminanthraquinone and its cyclised product ceramidone, reported as disperse dye on synthetic fibres⁵.

Synthesis of disperse dyes of the following general structure are reported,

where, R = phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *m*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-nitrophenyl, *m*-nitrophenyl, *p*-nitrophenyl, *o*-chlorophenyl, *m*-chlorophenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl.

Equimolar quantities of 8-aminoceramidone and cyanuric chloride were reacted. The product was further reacted with aryl urea derivatives to yield the disperse dyes.

Experimental

1-Amino-4-anilinoanthraquinone-2-sulphonic acid : A mixture of bromamine acid as sodium salt (4.04 g, 0.01 mol), aniline (0.93 g, 0.01 mol) and sodium carbonate (2.1 g) in water (50 ml) was heated to 70°. An aqueous solution of copper sulphate (0.5 g) and ferrous sulphate (0.5 g) was added to the mixture, the temperature was raised to 90° and heated at same temperature for 1 h. It was necessary to maintain basic media of reaction.

The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, filtered and washed with 20% sodium chloride (40 ml) to yield the product (80%).

1-Amino-4-anilinoanthraquinone : 1-Amino-4-anilinoanthraquinone-2-sulphonic acid (2.08 g, 0.005 mol) was dissolved in a solution of sodium hydroxide (1 g in 50 ml water) at 90–95°. A warm solution of glucose (1.7 g in 20 ml water) was then added dropwise and the mixture was heated at 95° for 1 h. It was then neutralised with concentrated HCl, the solid filtered, washed with hot water and recrystallised in toluene to yield the product (95%), m.p. 191°.

8-Aminoceramidone : A mixture of 1-amino-4-anilinoanthraquinone (3.14 g, 0.01 mol) and ortho-phosphoric acid (50 ml) was heated slowly at 200–210° for 4 h. The mixture was then neutralised with sodium carbonate, filtered, the solid washed with water, dried and recrystallised in chlorobenzene to yield the product (70%), m.p. 210°.

[2,4-Dichloro-6-yl-aminoceramidone]-s-triazine : A mixture of 8-aminoceramidone (2.96 g, 0.01 mol) and nitrobenzene (30 ml) was heated slowly to 80°. Then cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) was added slowly with stirring and the reaction mixture was refluxed at 140–150° for 4 h. The mixture was then cooled, filtered and the solid washed with nitrobenzene and recrystallised in toluene to yield the product (76%), m.p. 232°.

[2,4-Diarylyureido-6-yl-aminoceramidone]-s-triazine : 2,4-Dichloro-6-yl-aminoceramidone-s-triazine (4.44 g, 0.01 mol) was suspended in acetone (60 ml). Arylurea (0.02 mol) was then added to the suspension. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h maintaining pH 6.5–7 with sodium carbonate solution (10%, w/v). It was then cooled to room temperature and the solid was filtered, washed and purified from DMF–acetone.

Application of [2,4-diarylyureido-6-yl-aminoceramidone]-s-triazine on polyester fabrics in 2% shade :

A glycerin bath and laboratory high temperature beaker dyeing machine were used.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

R	Colour	M.p. °C	Yield %
Phenyl	Brownish yellow	254	68
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Brown	248	72
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Brown	262	74
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Brown	157	73
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	Orange brown	173	79
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	Orange brown	272	78
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Orange brown	130	81
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	Brownish yellow	215	64
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Brownish yellow	140	76
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Brownish yellow	185	65

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Preparation of dye bath : A paste of weighed quantity of dye (40 mg) was prepared with dispersing agent Dadamol (40 mg), wetting agent Tween-80 (5 mg) and water (1 ml). To it water (99 ml) was added with stirring and pH adjusted to 4 using a etic acid.

Dyeing process : The dye solution (100 ml) was added to a beaker provided with a lid and screw cap. Before closing the lid and tightening the metal cap over the beaker, wetted pattern of polyester was rolled properly and dropped into beaker. The beaker was then placed vertically on the rotatory carrier inside the tank and clamp plate was firmly tightened by the nut of the stud. The rotatory carrier was allowed to rotate in the glycerin bath ; the temperature of which was raised at a rate of 2° per min upto a final temperature of 130°. The dyeing was continued for 60 min at 130° under pressure. After cooling over a period of 1 h the beaker was removed from the bath and washed with water. The pattern was washed several times with cold water.

The above dyed pattern was further treated with a solution of the detergent (0.2 g) and sodium carbonate (0.1 g) in water (100 ml) at 80° for 30 min. After washing the pattern thoroughly with water, it was dried.

Determination of R_f values : (2,4-Diarylureido-6-ylaminoceramidone)-*s*-triazine were separated on

tlc using chloroform–methanol (95 : 5) solvent system. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

R	Shade on polyester	R_f	λ_{max}
Phenyl	Light brown	0.79	485
<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Brown red	0.76	490
<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Brown red	0.81	488
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Brown red	0.83	490
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellowish brown	0.84	400
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellowish brown	0.83	490
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellowish brown	0.80	490
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	Reddish brown	0.87	490
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Reddish brown	0.85	495
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Reddish brown	0.84	492

Determination of λ_{max} : λ_{max} of (2,4-diarylureido-6-ylaminoceramidone)-*s*-triazine were determined in DMF solution at 28°, using a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer and concentration of the dye solution was 2×10^{-2} . The results are given in Table 2.

Infrared spectroscopy (ir spectra) : Ir spectra of (2,4-diarylureido-6-ylaminoceramidone)-*s*-triazine derivatives reveal C=O stretching vibration at 1 660–1 695 and 1 610–1 630 cm^{-1} (w), C_8N_8 stretch at 775–810 cm^{-1} , NH stretch at 1 570–1 600 cm^{-1} and bonded NH–CO–NH stretch at 3 310–3 420 cm^{-1} (w, br).

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